

Effect of A Self-Efficacy Enhancing Program on Dietary and Exercise Behaviors in Patients with Coronary Artery Disease After Receiving Percutaneous Coronary Intervention Treatment

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Abstract

Background: Patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) who have undergone percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) need to change health behaviors which may pose risk factors for this condition. However, changing eating habits and adopting regular exercise remain areas of deficiency among this group. This is because these behaviors have been practiced for a long time and have become habitual, making them difficult to change. Most importantly, patients often lack confidence or self-efficacy in their ability to modify these behaviors. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance self-efficacy in this group to support dietary and exercise habit changes. **Purpose:** This study aimed to compare the dietary and exercise behaviors of CAD who have received PCI intervention treatment and a self-efficacy promotion program, and those who received standard care. **Methods:** This research is a quasi-experimental study using a two-group posttest design. Purposive sampling was used to recruit 56 patients with CAD who had received PCI at Petcharat Cardiac Intensive Care Unit 4C and Petcharat Ward 16B, Faculty of Medicine, Vajira Hospital, Navamindradhiraj University, between June 2024 and January 2025. Of these, 28 patients were assigned to a control group that received standard care, while the remaining 28 patients in the experimental group received a self-efficacy enhancing program on dietary and exercise behaviors. The research instruments included: 1) the General Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale; 2) a self-efficacy enhancing program on dietary and exercise behaviors; 3) a handbook on disease and appropriate health behavior regarding diet and exercise; 4) video media presenting a symbolic model on appropriate eating behavior; 5) video media presenting a symbolic model on appropriate exercise behavior; 6) a questionnaire on dietary behavior specific to cardiovascular disease; and 7) a questionnaire on exercise behavior of patients with acute myocardial infarction after undergoing coronary angioplasty. Analysis of data was conducted using descriptive statistics, and the Mann-Whitney U and independent t-test. **Results:** The experimental group which received the self-efficacy enhancing program had significantly higher scores for both dietary and exercise behaviors compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusions:** These results indicate that the program is effective in promoting healthy eating and exercise behaviors in patients with CAD after PCI. Therefore, this program should be integrated into standard care for this patient group.

Keywords: Coronary Artery Disease, Percutaneous Coronary Intervention, Dietary And Exercise Behaviors, A Self-Efficacy Enhancing Program.

BACKGROUND

Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) is a complex, chronic condition and one of the leading causes of death globally, particularly in the Asia-Pacific region, where the mortality rate accounts for up to 58% of the global total (WHO, 2020). In Thailand, CAD ranks among the top three causes of death (Office of the Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Public Health, 2021). The number of patients has continued to rise each year, reflecting the severity of this current public health issue.

The primary treatment approach aims to restore effective blood flow to the heart muscle by opening blocked coronary arteries. One widely used method is Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI), which has been shown to reduce hospital stay durations, lower mortality rates, and increase survival rates to as high as 90.16% (CCIT, 2019). Despite its effectiveness, patients remain at risk of restenosis, particularly at the site of stent placement (in-stent restenosis, or ISR).

Post-treatment care must therefore emphasize health behavior modification, including dietary management, regular exercise, weight control, smoking cessation, stress management, and consistent medication adherence. However, literature reviews reveal that many patients still struggle to fully adopt these health behaviors, particularly regarding diet and physical activity. These shortcomings significantly increase the risk of recurrent arterial blockage—by as much as 12.72 and 12 times, respectively—compared to those who adhere to appropriate health behaviors (Supawan et al., 2019; Nazeri et al., 2020). Health behavior modification after PCI is a complex process that does not occur immediately. It depends on individual and environmental factors influencing one's readiness and ability to maintain appropriate health behaviors (Pender et al., 2011; Lawton et al., 2021). A key factor is self-efficacy, or the belief in one's own ability, which is central to Bandura's theory (1997).

Self-efficacy directly impacts successful behavior change and is influenced by internal factors such as gender, age, education, income, and occupation, as well as external factors like support from healthcare professionals and social networks (Wolf et al., 2019; Onge & Krueger, 2017). Numerous studies have shown that enhancing self-efficacy is positively associated with improved health behaviors in patients with CAD (Dechkaew et al., 2021; Alizadeh et al., 2018).

The literature review reveals applications of self-efficacy theory in promoting dietary and exercise behaviors. For example, a study by Promphiw et al. (2015) found that after a 12-week intervention based on this theory, participants demonstrated increased self-efficacy and improved exercise ability. However, the study lacked continuous follow-up, which affected the long-term consistency of behavior. To address this issue, the researcher developed a self-efficacy enhancement program incorporating regular follow-ups through the LINE application. Notifications are particularly effective for patients who need to adopt new behaviors, as they help maintain consistency (Charoenwongsa et al., 2022; Nakornriap et al., 2017; Dale et al., 2015).

The program also integrates confidence-building activities, such as adopting a Mediterranean diet, participating in group discussions on appropriate eating-out behaviors (since patients often choose foods unsuitable for their condition when dining out; Nasungchon, 2010; Suwanrat, 2009), and using wrist-based pulse monitoring to calculate maximum heart rate during exercise. These activities aim to empower patients to believe they can successfully change their dietary and exercise habits.

The self-efficacy enhancement program was developed based on Bandura's concept, utilizing four key sources of self-efficacy: (1) mastery experiences, (2) vicarious experiences, (3) verbal persuasion, and (4) physiological and emotional states. Consistent follow-up via the LINE application was also incorporated to reinforce confidence, which is expected to lead to sustained improvements in diet- and exercise-related health behaviors among post-PCI patients.

METHODS

Study Design

This research used a quasi-experimental approach with a two-group posttest design.

Sample/Participants

The study was conducted with patients diagnosed with CAD who had undergone PCI at the Petcharat Cardiac Intensive Care Unit 4C and Petcharat Ward 16B, Faculty of Medicine, Vajira Hospital, Navamindradhiraj University. The inclusion criteria were: 1) aged between 40-75 years; 2) underwent PCI for the first time, with one or more arteries treated; 3) had a self-efficacy perception score ranging from low to moderate, as measured by Sukmak et al. (2002); 4) able to read, speak, write, and communicate in Thai proficiently; 5) owned a smartphone with internet access and able to use the LINE application independently; and 6) willing to participate in the research study. The sample size was determined using an effect size of 0.5. This value was then used to refer to the sample size table by Burn and Grove (2009), with a significance level of 0.05 and a power of 0.80 (Polit & Beck, 2004). Based on these parameters, a sample size of 22 participants per group was required, totaling 44 participants. To account for potential attrition during data collection, the researcher increased the sample size by 20%. As a result, the final sample consisted of 56 participants, with 28 in the experimental group and 28 in the control group.

Instruments

The research instruments included:

1. The General Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995) was translated into Thai by Sukmak et al. (2002) and consists of 10 positively-worded items. It assesses individuals' confidence in handling unexpected situations, overcoming challenges, and managing health-related issues. Responses are rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at all true) to 4 (Exactly true). Total scores range from 10 to 40. Scores below 29 indicate low self-efficacy, 29–34 indicate moderate self-efficacy, and scores of 35 or higher indicate high self-efficacy.

2. A self-efficacy enhancing program targeting dietary and exercise behaviors was developed based on Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy framework and relevant literature. The program consisted of the following components:

2.1 Promoting the successful completion of specific activities: By doing this, patients themselves can enhance their confidence in managing their own health in daily life.

These activities include: 1) a dietary aspect: practicing appropriate meal preparation, reading nutrition labels, and choosing suitable food options when eating out, tailored to their health condition, and 2) an exercise aspect: monitoring pulse rate, calculating heart rate, and performing a three-phase exercise routine—warm-up, endurance walking, and cool-down stretching. These activities provide patients with hands-on experiences that can be realistically applied in their everyday lives.

2.2 Promoting vicarious experience through symbolic modeling: Patients observed symbolic models through video media, featuring individuals with similar characteristics who had successfully adopted appropriate dietary and exercise behaviors. These models shared personal stories, including challenges, solutions, and motivational messages, which helped enhance patients' attention, memory retention, and self-belief in adopting similar behaviors.

2.3 Promoting verbal persuasion: Verbal encouragement was provided to build patients' confidence in their ability to adopt the desired behaviors, even if immediate success was not achieved. This included verbal

guidance, motivation, praise, and reassurance during program activities. Additionally, individualized supportive messages were sent via the LINE application while patients practiced activities at home.

2.4 Promoting physiological and affective states: Patients were encouraged to self-assess their physical readiness before engaging in activities by checking for chest pain, absence of fever, and normal pulse rate. They were also taught how to manage any abnormal symptoms. Additionally, reflective techniques were used to help patients recognize their own sense of self-efficacy regarding dietary and exercise behaviors.

The program consisted of an individual session in the first phase, followed by small group sessions in the second and third phases. Participants were also assigned home-based activities for a duration of eight weeks. The total intervention period was 12 weeks, with outcome evaluations conducted at the end of the program. This program has undergone content validation by qualified experts with specialized knowledge in the field.

3. An electronic handbook on coronary artery disease and appropriate health behaviors related to diet and exercise was developed based on the literature review. It included content on CAD definition, coronary angioplasty, risk factors for restenosis, and recommended lifestyle practices. The handbook was validated by experts and pilot-tested with two patients sharing characteristics similar to the target population to ensure clarity of content and language prior to implementation.

4. Video media presenting a symbolic model on appropriate eating behavior was developed by the researcher. This video featured a post-PCI coronary artery disease patient who successfully adopted healthy eating habits. The patient shared personal experiences, challenges, and coping strategies, with persuasive communication to build confidence in dietary behavior change. The video was content-validated by six experts and pilot-tested with two patients similar to the target sample. Results showed it was easy to understand and suitable for use with the study participants.

5. Video media presenting a symbolic model on appropriate exercise behavior by Ashton (2008) featured a CAD patient post-PCI who had successfully adopted regular exercise. It covered the patient's experiences, benefits of exercise, common barriers, and coping strategies, using persuasive communication to boost viewers' confidence in exercising appropriately.

6. A questionnaire on dietary behavior specific to cardiovascular disease, developed by Maegaret (2003) and translated into Thai by Tantikusum (2010), consisted of 16 questions. These questions assessed the restriction of fat, cholesterol, and salt intake, as well as the increase in fiber consumption. The responses are based on a 5-point rating scale, ranging from 1 point (Never consume this type of food) to 5 points (Consume every day). The total score ranges from 16 to 80. A higher total score indicates better dietary behavior specific to cardiovascular disease, while a lower total score indicates poorer dietary behavior. The questionnaire was pilot-tested with 10 patients who shared similar characteristics to the target sample. The Cronbach's alpha was 0.81

7. A questionnaire on exercise behavior of patients with acute myocardial infarction after undergoing coronary angioplasty by Lanwong (2015) consisted of 16 questions. These questions assessed the type, intensity, duration, frequency of exercise, and other exercise-related practices. The questionnaire includes 15 positively-worded questions and one negatively-worded question, for which the scores are reversed. The responses are based on a rating scale, ranging from 1 point (Never perform) to 3 points (Always perform). The total score ranges from 16 to 48 points. A higher total score indicates a high level of exercise behavior, while a lower total score indicates a low level of exercise behavior. The questionnaire was pilot-tested with 10 patients who shared similar characteristics to the target sample. The Cronbach alpha was 0.82

Data Collection

The researcher personally conducted data collection from June 2024 to January 2025 at Petcharat Cardiac Intensive Care Unit 4C and Petcharat Ward 16B, Faculty of Medicine, Vajira Hospital, Navamindradhiraj University. The control group was completed first, followed by the experimental group, as follows:

Control Group: The researcher conducted data collection, in sequence, as follows:

1. Time 1 (Day 1 after PCI): The researcher met with each participant individually at the patient's ward for 10 minutes. Participants completed a personal information form, and a follow-up phone call was scheduled. Afterward, they received routine care from the ward nurses.

On the final day of Week 12 after PCI, the researcher contacted participants by phone at home to complete the dietary and exercise behavior questionnaires. The program was concluded, and participants were thanked for their cooperation in the study.

Experimental Group: The researcher conducted data collection, in sequence, as follows:

1. Time 1 (Day 1 after PCI): The individual session lasted 60 minutes and included the following activities: 1) rapport building, general symptom check, and vital signs assessment; 2) participants completed a personal information form, and the researcher gave an overview of the program; 3) education about coronary artery disease (CAD), diet, and exercise behaviors was provided; and 4) the researcher had the participants watch two videos about a successful role model for dietary and exercise behaviors. After watching, participants discussed how to apply the strategies to their own lives.

2. Time 2 (Week 2 after PCI): A group activity (4–5 participants) was conducted at the outpatient department (OPD) for 45 minutes and included the following activities: 1) checking general symptoms and assessing vital signs; 2) watching the same two videos again to reinforce the guidance provided by the role model; 3) demonstrating Mediterranean-style meal preparation, reading nutrition labels, and measuring sodium and sugar content—participants then practiced these skills through backward demonstration; 4) participating in a group discussion on the topic “How to Eat Out Appropriately”; and 5) receiving a demonstration on how to palpate the radial artery at the wrist to assess heart rate, followed by a demonstration of exercise practices (including warm-up, active, and cool-down phases) with a backward demonstration method. After the group session, participants were instructed to carry out the following self-care activities at home:

2.1) Participants were instructed to record all foods consumed at each meal using a food behavior log, noting the following: 1) food consumed (specify whether the food was homemade, purchased, or pre-packaged) and sodium, salt, fish sauce, soy sauce, or sugar intake (record the amount of these ingredients consumed at each meal.)

2.2) Exercise Behavior Practice: Participants were instructed to engage in regular physical activity at least 3–5 times per week, with each session lasting 30–45 minutes. Each session should include warm-up, active, and cool-down phases as demonstrated during the group session. Participants were also encouraged to palpate their radial artery before and after exercise to monitor their heart rate.

2.3) Participants were asked to sit and record their exercise behaviors using an exercise log. The log should include the following: 1) heart rate before exercise: record the heart rate prior to starting exercise; 2) maximum heart rate: record the maximum heart rate calculated during exercise; 3) heart rate after exercise: record the heart rate immediately after exercise, and 4) any abnormal symptoms: note any unusual symptoms experienced during exercise. This log helps track cardiovascular responses and potential issues during physical activity.

2.4) Participants were added on LINE for ongoing motivation and guidance. They used the electronic manual and logs to track their diet and exercise. The researcher provided continuous support and scheduled the next meeting.

3. Time 3 (Week 4 after PCI): A group activity (4–5 participants) was conducted at the outpatient department (OPD) for 10 minutes and included the following activities: 1) the researcher built rapport with participants, asked about their general health, and assessed chest pain and vital signs to promote self-efficacy in terms of physical and emotional states; 2) participants reflected on their confidence in performing dietary and

exercise behaviors; and 3) the researcher concluded the session, emphasizing the importance of continuing behaviors until Week 12 and scheduling the final session.

On the final day of Week 12 after PCI, the researcher contacted the participants via telephone. The call lasted approximately 10 minutes, during which the participants were asked to complete a dietary behavior questionnaire and an exercise behavior questionnaire. The researcher then expressed gratitude for their cooperation in the study and informed them of the conclusion of both the activities and the research.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS statistical software. Personal data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The differences in personal data between groups were compared using the chi-square test and Fisher’s exact test. The comparison of mean dietary behavior scores between the group that received the program and the group that received routine nursing care was analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U test. The comparison of mean exercise behavior scores between the program group and the routine care group was analyzed using an independent t-test.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted with the approval of the Research Ethics Committee of the Nursing Faculty, Chiang Mai University (Approval No 2567-EXP005) and the Human Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Medicine Vajira Hospital, Navamindradhiraj University (Approval No: 063/67 FB). After receiving the hospital director’s approval to collect data, the researcher provided the participants with information regarding the study’s objectives, methods, and instruments, as well as confidentiality management and their right to withdraw from the study.

RESULTS

Demographic Data of the Participants

As shown in Table 1, both groups consisted of 57.14% females and 42.86% males. The control group ranged in age from 40 to 70 years (Mean = 63, SD = 10.06), and the experimental group from 45 to 70 years (Mean = 60, SD = 8.31). Most participants were married (60.71%). In the control group, employment status was evenly split (50.00%), while 71.43% of the experimental group were employed. In both groups, 64.29% had at least a secondary education. Regarding income, 78.57% of the control group and 57.14% of the experimental group had a household income below 30,000 THB/month. The majority in both groups were classified as obese (57.14% and 53.57%, respectively) and had comorbidities (75.00% and 78.57%, respectively). Most had no prior history of exercise (78.57% and 75.00%), no history of alcohol consumption (92.86% in both), and no smoking history (89.29% and 85.71%, respectively). Additionally, 78.57% and 82.14% had no exposure to secondhand smoke. Chi-square and Fisher’s exact tests showed no significant differences in general characteristics between the two groups.

Table 1: Comparison of Participant Characteristics Between the Control and Experimental Groups (n = 56)

Characteristics	Control Group (n = 28)		Experimental Group (n = 28)		X ²	p-value*
	Number (n)	Percent (%)	Number (n)	Percent (%)		
Sex					0.00 ^a	1.00 ^{ns}
Female	16	57.14	16	57.14		
Male	12	42.86	12	42.86		
Age (years)					0.64 ^a	0.42 ^{ns}
< 60 years	12	42.86	15	53.57		
≥ 60 years	16	57.14	13	46.43		
Min - Max, Mean □, S.D.	40-70, 63, 10.06		45-70, 60, 8.31			
Marital Status					0.00 ^a	1.00 ^{ns}
Single/Divorced/Widowed	11	39.29	11	39.29		
Married	17	60.71	17	60.71		

Occupation						
Unemployed	14	50.00	8	28.57	0.26 ^a	0.10 ^{ns}
Employed	14	50.00	20	71.43		
Education Level						
Primary school or below	10	35.71	10	35.71	0.00 ^a	1.00 ^{ns}
Secondary school or above	18	64.29	18	64.29		
Average Monthly Household Income (2023)						
< 30,000 THB	22	78.57	16	57.14	2.94 ^a	0.08 ^{ns}
≥ 30,000 THB	6	21.43	12	42.86		
Body Mass Index (BMI)						
Normal	5	17.86	9	32.14		
Overweight	7	25.00	4	14.29		
Obese	16	57.14	15	53.57		
Comorbidity						
No comorbidity	7	25.00	6	21.43	0.10 ^a	0.75 ^{ns}
With comorbidity	21	75.00	21	78.57		
History of Exercise						
No	22	78.57	21	75.00	0.10 ^a	0.75 ^{ns}
Yes	6	21.43	7	25.00		
History of Alcohol Consumption						
No	26	92.86	26	92.86	0.00 ^b	1.0 ^{ns}
Yes	2	7.14	2	7.14		
Smoking History						
No	25	89.29	24	85.71	0.16 ^b	1.0 ^{ns}
Yes	3	10.71	4	14.29		
History of Secondhand Smoke Exposure						
No	22	78.57	23	82.14	0.11 ^a	0.73 ^{ns}
Yes	6	21.43	5	17.86		

Note. a = Chi-square test, b = Fisher’s Exact test, ns = Not significant

Comparison of mean dietary behavior scores between the control group and the experimental group

As shown in Table 2, The Mann–Whitney U test was used to compare the mean scores of dietary behavior between the control group and the experimental group after the intervention. The results revealed that the experimental group, which received the self-efficacy enhancement program, had significantly higher dietary behavior scores than the control group, which received routine nursing care. This difference was statistically significant at the .05 level.

Table 2: Comparison of the Mean Differences in Dietary Behaviors Between the Control and Experimental Groups (N = 56)

Dietary Behavior	Control Group (n =28)		Experimental Group (n = 28)		t	p-value*
	M	IQR	M	IQR		
After intervention	37.00	4.00	59.00	1.00	-6.48	.001**

Note. * p < .05, ** p < .001, M = Median, IQR = Interquartile Range

Comparison of mean exercise behavior scores between the control group and the experimental group

As shown in Table 3, an independent t-test was used to compare the mean scores of exercise behavior between the control group and the experimental group after the intervention. The results showed that the experimental group, which received the self-efficacy enhancement program, had significantly higher exercise behavior scores than the control group, which received routine nursing care. This difference was statistically significant at the .05 level.

Table 3: Comparison of the Mean Differences in Exercise Behaviors Between the Control and Experimental Groups (N = 56)

Exercise Behavior	Control Group (n =28)		Experimental Group (n = 28)		t	p-value*
	M	IQR	M	IQR		
After intervention	21.00	8.50	43.50	3.00	-22.94	.001**

Note. * p < .05, ** p < .001, M = Median, IQR = Interquartile Range

DISCUSSION

Summary of the findings

This study examined the effects of a self-efficacy promotion program on dietary and exercise behaviors in patients with CAD following coronary angioplasty. The findings revealed that the experimental group receiving the self-efficacy enhancement program in conjunction with standard nursing care showed significantly higher mean scores in dietary and exercise behaviors post-intervention compared to the control group receiving only standard nursing care, with statistical significance at the .05 level, as shown in Tables 2 and 3. These results support the research hypothesis and demonstrate that the self-efficacy promotion program enhanced participants' confidence in their own abilities, thereby facilitating behavioral changes in diet and exercise. The program was developed based on Bandura's (1997) theory of self-efficacy and a literature review, incorporating activities that promote the four sources of self-efficacy:

1. Mastery Experiences

The program provided information and knowledge about CAD, recurrence risk factors, and dietary and exercise behavior guidelines. Beyond education, the researcher used demonstrations and had participants practice and repeat specific health behaviors to enable independent application. These included preparing Mediterranean-style meals, reading nutrition labels, measuring sugar and salt intake using measuring spoons, engaging on "How to Eat Out Properly," checking radial pulse, calculating heart rate before and after exercise to assess readiness, and engaging in appropriate exercise phases. These activities equipped participants with skills, increased their confidence, and empowered them to independently apply healthy eating and exercise behaviors in daily life. Participants developed confidence in changing their dietary and exercise behaviors through the use of self-monitoring tools, such as food and exercise behavior logs. Dietary logs included categories such as types of food consumed (homemade, purchased, ready-to-eat), amounts of sodium/salt/fish sauce/soy sauce, and sugar intake. These logs helped clarify dietary patterns, such as excessive salt or sugar consumption, and encouraged mindful eating when dining out. Exercise logs tracked pre-exercise heart rate, estimated maximum heart rate (220-age multiplied by 0.5–0.7), post-exercise heart rate, and any abnormal symptoms during exercise. These logs supported confidence-building through consistent self-monitoring, body awareness, and active participation. As a result, participants perceived their actions as successful, reinforcing the belief that they were capable of achieving desired outcomes, consistent with Bandura's theory (1997).

2. Vicarious Experiences (Modeling)

The researcher used video media to present live models, which aligns with Bandura's (1997) theories of observational learning and self-efficacy. Observing the success of similar individuals helped participants build confidence through vicarious experience.

The first video featured a patient successfully engaging in post-treatment exercise, providing an image of someone "like themselves" who had regained health, thereby inspiring and motivating participants to believe they could achieve similar outcomes. According to Bandura, observing individuals with similar characteristics enhances self-confidence.

The second video used symbolic modeling to present appropriate dietary behaviors, emphasizing important content in an organized manner, which enhanced comprehension, retention, and application of the desired behaviors. Post-viewing group discussions further reinforced motivation. For example, when discussing eating out, participants suggested modifying meals like yellow egg noodle seafood Yen Ta Fo by substituting white rice noodles to reduce carbohydrates, avoiding meatballs, skipping added sugar or fish sauce, and not drinking the soup to reduce sodium intake. This group activity supported the motivational processes described by Bandura, where social reinforcement and peer support enhance the likelihood of behavior implementation.

3. Verbal Persuasion

The researcher used verbal encouragement, praise, and motivation throughout the program, both during sessions and via the LINE application. Positive reinforcement included praise for successful behavior, encouragement during uncertainty or mistakes, and motivation when encountering obstacles. This helped reduce discouragement and boosted determination, especially in participants with low confidence or anxiety. Consistent supportive messages via LINE fostered a sense of being valued and supported, positively influencing attitudes and internal motivation. This aligns with Bandura's idea that verbal persuasion can enhance self-efficacy, particularly when combined with modeling and mastery experiences.

4. Physiological and Emotional States

The researcher created a relaxed and friendly environment through greetings and casual conversations, reducing stress and promoting comfort. Physical assessments (temperature, pulse, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation) reassured participants of their physical readiness for activity. Reflective discussions helped participants connect their emotions and beliefs with their capabilities—such as confidence in dietary control or recalling positive exercise experiences. All patients reported confidence in their ability to adopt healthy behaviors, reinforced by daily practice and logging. This aligns with Bandura's theory that individuals use emotional and physiological states to judge their capability; feeling relaxed, energetic, and emotionally positive enhances confidence, while stress or discomfort can undermine it, regardless of actual ability.

These findings are consistent with previous research applying Bandura's self-efficacy theory, such as the study by Promphiw et al. (2015) which found increased self-efficacy led to behavioral changes in diet and exercise. In this study, the researcher applied all four sources of self-efficacy into practical, continuous, and supportive activities. Participants received consistent encouragement and reminders via LINE over 12 weeks, promoting positive reinforcement and reflective practice to help reinforce self-awareness. Daily behavioral records also served as evidence of "success" or "effort," gradually building confidence with the mindset, "I've done it before, I can do it again."

As a result, the experimental group achieved significantly better dietary and exercise behaviors than the control group receiving only standard care. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that a self-efficacy promotion program based on Bandura's theory (1997) combined with a literature review, effectively enhances self-efficacy in patients with CAD after angioplasty. By integrating mastery experiences, modeling, verbal persuasion, and regulation of physiological and emotional states, the program successfully boosted participants' self-confidence, leading to positive changes in dietary and exercise behaviors.

Limitations

In this study, the intervention was implemented over a 12-week period, and the outcomes were assessed immediately upon completion of the program. Consequently, it remains inconclusive whether participants had developed a sustained and authentic sense of self-efficacy. It is recommended that the outcomes of the self-efficacy enhancement program be monitored for at least four weeks after the program's completion to assess the sustainability of its effects.

Implications for Nursing Practice

The self-efficacy enhancement program, including an educational manual on coronary artery disease and guidelines for healthy behaviors related to diet and exercise, as well as the use of a LINE Official Account (Line OA) for motivation, reminders, and follow-up, should be proposed to relevant healthcare agencies for consideration as a guideline for patients with CAD undergoing their first PCI. Training should be provided for nurses who will implement the self-efficacy enhancement program to ensure their readiness prior to applying the program in patient care.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the self-efficacy promotion program is effective in promoting healthy eating and exercise behaviors in patients with CAD after PCI. Therefore, this program should be integrated into standard care for this patient group.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

All authors declared no potential conflict of interest in the study.

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